

STUDENT PERCEPTIONS OF STUDENT SUPPORT SERVICES FOR FIRST-YEAR ENGINEERING STUDENTS (CONCEPT)

A. Van Dyck¹

KU Leuven, LESEC, Faculty of Engineering Technology, Campus De Nayer
Sint-Katelijne-Waver, Belgium
0000-0002-9635-289X

E. Koppen

KU Leuven, LESEC, Faculty of Engineering Technology, Campus De Nayer
Sint-Katelijne-Waver, Belgium

L. Van den Broeck

KU Leuven, LESEC, Faculty of Engineering Technology, Campus De Nayer
Sint-Katelijne-Waver, Belgium
0000-0002-6276-7501

G. Langie

KU Leuven, LESEC, Faculty of Engineering Technology, Campus De Nayer
Sint-Katelijne-Waver, Belgium
0000-0002-9061-6727

Conference Key Areas: *Student Engagement, Mentorship and Tutorship*

Keywords: *student support services, first year, student perception, study success*

ABSTRACT

To help first-year students get accustomed to university, many universities organise intra- and extracurricular support initiatives. During the academic year, student support services at the Faculty of Engineering Technology at KU Leuven offer both course-specific activities as well as initiatives focusing on study career guidance and academic skills. Yet we notice that not all students find their way to these voluntary activities – even if they would benefit from the help.

The purpose of this study is (1) to understand how first-year engineering students perceive the student support services, and (2) to understand how we can reach

¹ A. Van Dyck, annelies.vandyck1@kuleuven.be

students who need the support, but do not find their way yet. This will further guide us in the development and communication of support activities.

A small-scale questionnaire was distributed among first-year engineering students, followed by two focus group discussions.

Our findings indicate that support needs are bigger at the start and end of the first semester. Crucial information such as how to study, and communication regarding support activities, should be served more than once, as first-year students still find it hard to filter out the right information. Students prefer course-specific Q&A sessions where they can hear questions of fellow students as well as the answers to those questions. A mentor for study career guidance is well appreciated. Tests and trial exams are important as triggers to start studying. We believe that these findings can inspire colleagues in other institutions.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Student support activities

All first-year university students face a daunting task: besides getting accustomed at a new environment, with new friends, they also need to quickly adapt to the teaching methods and tempo at their new college [1]. Across the globe, universities are therefore seeking ways to accommodate their first-year students with support activities [1,2,3]. In Belgium, many of these activities are non-compulsory.

For specific studies, such as engineering technology, Belgian students are obliged to take a non-binding diagnostic math test before they can enroll. However, Belgian regulations stipulate an open enrollment system for most study areas including engineering technology, so the diagnostic test is low-stakes. As a result, many students start their engineering studies with underpreparedness for math [5].

Student support includes a rich variety of possible activities in response to local needs [6,7]. At the Faculty of Engineering Technology (FET) at KU Leuven, the support activities are arranged roughly into two categories: course-specific activities such as Q&A sessions and basic mathematical skill courses, and activities that surpass the course-specificity such as academic skills interventions and study career guidance. We will call the latter 'non-course-specific support'.

FET is a multi-campus faculty. In this study, we focus on the student perception of both categories of student support activities at KU Leuven Campus De Nayer, one of the seven campuses of FET.

1.2 Student support activities at KU Leuven Campus De Nayer

At Campus De Nayer, students are divided into study groups of around 20 students who follow exercises and laboratory sessions together. Theory lectures and Q&A sessions are taken by all students at the same time, regardless of study group. Typical for the campus is the relatively high number of commuting students: 70% of first-year students in 2021-2022 travel over 10 km to the campus on a daily basis.

In Table 1, we describe the support activities that were offered to first-year students at Campus De Nayer in the first semester of academic year 2021-2022.

Table 1. First-year student support activities, KU Leuven Campus De Nayer (2021-2022)

Activity	Description
<i>Course-specific activities in the first semester</i>	
Q&A session	Voluntary group session. Students can ask questions about the course material. Each course offers at least two Q&A sessions per semester. Just before the first and second exam periods, an extra Q&A session takes place ('Return Day').
Tests	Compulsory tests in November that partially count in the exam score, depending on the result and the course.
Trial Exam	Voluntary non-binding test imitating an exam. Each course is represented with one question.
Basic mathematics skill courses	Voluntary mathematics support, consisting of a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) and an online support trajectory on basic mathematics
<i>Non-course-specific activities in the first semester</i>	
Starters Days	Compulsory two-day activity at the start of the academic year. Campus life and practical tools are explained, PhD students show the link between their research and the courses, and first-year students have a chance to get to know each other.
LASSI Workshop	Compulsory test and workshop at the beginning of the semester. LASSI stands for Learning And Study Strategies Inventory. Topics include time management, study method, motivation, etc.
Workshop Time Management	Voluntary in-depth workshop following the LASSI workshop.
Workshop Efficient Study Methods	Voluntary in-depth workshop following the LASSI workshop.
Tutoring by staff	A mentor is assigned to each study group. The mentor helps with study-related questions, follow up on results, and is a coach for study-related questions. An individual mentor meeting is offered after the tests and after each exam period.
Tutoring by peers	Two higher-year students per study group help the first-year students get accustomed to university life and the campus.
Online modules	Online modules and training videos on study planning, fear of failure, procrastination, etc.

The goal of the study was two-fold: (1) Starting from the current support activities (both course-specific and non-course-specific), we wanted to know, from a student's perspective, which are the essential building blocks. (2) Moreover, we were looking

for inspiration on how we can reach students who need the support, but do not find their way to the current support activities.

2 METHODOLOGY

We used a mixed method, starting with a small-scale questionnaire to help us find the right qualitative questions. Subsequently, we ran two focus groups. As we were primarily looking for student perceptions, we relied on self-report data. Self-reports are subject to a number of biases, so insights should be interpreted with care.

2.1 Small-scale questionnaire

In the small-scale questionnaire (41 students; response rate = 42%), we explored three themes: (1) feeling of support at the beginning of the studies, (2) knowledge of and participation in support activities, and (3) support activity preference (ranking). The questionnaire was offered on a voluntary basis during a theory lecture, and was administered via PollEverywhere. The English translation to the questions in the questionnaire is listed in the Appendix.

2.2 Focus groups

Based on the questionnaire results, we explored emerging themes in more depth in the focus groups (n=10). We invited students from two study groups with different characteristics in order to have a good mix of students who attended the student support activities, and students who need the support but did not yet find their way. All students were invited to participate on a voluntary basis.

3 RESULTS

In this concept paper, we will focus on the insights that are most striking and that will guide us in rethinking student support and communication, based on student perception and self-reported needs.

3.1 Results of the questionnaire

Overall, students report they felt well-supported when starting their studies. As Fig. 1 shows, 69% of students felt supported to very supported at the start of their studies.

Fig. 1. First-year student response to the question how supported they felt in general at the beginning of their studies.

Table 2 shows that self-reported knowledge of the course-specific activities is high for most activities (known by 78%-95% of respondents), except for Return Day (49%). As for self-reported student attendance of these activities, we see a remarkably low reported attendance rate of Q&A sessions with respect to reported

knowledge of the sessions. In the open-ended question on course-specific activities (no. 5 in Table 5), we found that 6 out of 18 students ask for 'group Q&A sessions'.

Table 2. Percentage of students claiming to know or have participated in a selection of course-specific support activities.

Course-specific activity	Know by	Attended by
Q&A session Fundamentals of Math.	95%	63%
Q&A session Chemistry	80%	37%
Trial Exam	88%	76%
Tests	78%	78%
Return Day	49%	29%

Looking at the the non-course-specific activities (Table 3), we learn that the individual mentor meeting, which is part of the tutoring by staff, is well appreciated: it is best known and attended by students. Moreover, in the ranking question (no. 8 in Table 5), the individual mentor meeting came out as the top student preference.

Knowledge of both the compulsory LASSI-workshop and the Starters Days is low (known by 51% and 68%, respectively). In the open-ended question on non-course specific activities (no. 9 in Table 5), 3 out of 11 students reported the need for more communication regarding these activities, e.g. reminders.

Table 3. Percentage of students claiming to know or have participated in a selection of non-course-specific support activities.

Non-course-specific Activity	Know by	Attended by
Tutoring by staff: individual mentor meeting after the tests / first exam period	85%	61%
Starters Days	68%	56%
LASSI Workshop	51%	29%

3.2 Discussion of questionnaire results

The reported feeling of being well-supported at the start of the academic year stands out, in particular as it contrasts with the fact that that not all students find their way to student support activities. This raises the question how the perception of support evolved throughout the semester.

The spontaneous request for 'group Q&A sessions' is striking, since Q&A-sessions are organised in group by default. This suggests the need for a closer look into how these sessions are organised, and what students would need.

The high appreciation of the individual mentor meeting made us wonder if the same appreciation holds true for tutoring by staff in general and for the tutoring by peers.

As for the low reported knowledge and attendance rates for both the course-specific Return Day and the non-course-specific LASSI-workshop and Starter's Days: we know from the attendance numbers that, contrary to what is reported by the students, most of them did attend these activities. Yet, only about half to a third of

the students who participated in the questionnaire report that they have attended. This suggests that the activities themselves might be well-known, but their names are not. Moreover, we wanted to better understand why some students asked for more communication regarding non-course-specific activities specifically.

The questionnaire findings hence led to the following focus group questions:

- How did your feeling of being supported by the campus evolve during the first semester?
- In the first semester, what were reasons to go to / skip the Q&A sessions?
- Which non-course-specific activities were communicated well? Which were not communicated well? Why is that so?
- Which questions would you ask your mentor? Which would you ask your peer tutor?

Since one of the goals of the study was to look for inspiration on how to reach students who need the support, but do not find their way to the activities yet, we decided to add one more question to the focus group discussion :

- What, if anything, would make you start studying sooner?

3.3 Focus group insights

All students in the focus groups reported that the feeling of being supported persisted throughout the first semester.

The need for support decreases as the students become more familiar with the campus: *“The first time you come in a laboratory, you don’t really know the teachers and you don’t dare to ask a question. That is different in the last lab, when you know them and the barrier to ask questions is smaller.”* However, the need for support increases again towards the end of the semester, as the first exam period comes closer. Several students report that they appreciated the information on how to deal with exam periods and the corresponding study blocks. As one student said: *“It’s the first time that we have to study two weeks in a row without doing anything else.”* This information should be given just in time: *“In the beginning of the semester, you don’t think about the need to start studying in a few months and how you could do that.”*

Yet, support can still be improved from student’s point of view. Students from one focus group reported that they did not know how to study their course material. One student suggested to organize a session where all lecturers would indicate what is important and how they expect students to study, referring to similar activities in secondary school. This shows that the process of getting used to independent study is still in full swing.

Table 4 lists reasons to attend or skip voluntary Q&A sessions in the first semester. As mentioned before, Q&A sessions are organised in group, yet several respondents to the questionnaire spontaneously asked for ‘group Q&A sessions’. When probed for the Q&A sessions, several students say they attend group Q&A sessions, even if they do not have any questions. Listening to the questions of fellow students – and the answers – helps them understand the course material better.

Yet, students report that in some Q&A sessions, questions are answered face to face rather than in group, so these sessions are not perceived as group sessions. Students consider this a missed opportunity: *“It’s always interesting when you hear other people’s questions, because then you think – Oh yeah, I did have the same question! But if you don’t hear them, they can’t help you. So I stopped attending those sessions.”*

Students of both focus groups emphasized the need for good planning of the Q&A sessions. This is related to the relatively high number of commuting students at Campus De Nayer. As one student said: *“If the Q&A is planned at 8.15 am, I need to catch the train at 6.50 am and I have to get out of bed at 6 am, which I find hard. So I tell myself: it’s just one question – why bother?”*

Table 4. Reasons (not) to attend the course-related Q&A sessions as claimed by students.

Reasons to attend	Reasons not to attend
Curiosity (very first Q&A session)	Too early / late in the day
To ask a question	No other activities planned before or after the session
To listen to questions of other students	No questions / haven’t studied course yet
Difficult course (e.g. mathematics)	Questions are answered individually only

Students seem to be okay with the communication of non-course-specific activities in general. When asked for ways to improve, several students say they wish to receive information through multiple channels, e.g. not only a note in the digital learning environment, but also an e-mail, a calendar item and/or a mention during one of the lectures. This confirms the data from the questionnaire, which suggested the need for reminders. Students say they are swamped by information, and believe that multiple-channel communication will help them filter out the important messages.

As suggested by the questionnaire data, some activity names appeared to be lesser known than the activities themselves. This was confirmed in the focus groups where students said a few times that they did not remember an activity, while when explained what it was, they admitted to have attended it. We believe this shows that activity names could be clearer. One activity should be referred to by one name only.

As for the interaction with their mentor (staff tutor), the focus groups confirmed the questionnaire findings as several students pointed out that they enjoy the interaction. Most students did not bring specific questions when they met individually with their mentor, yet they appreciated the information given about (trial) exam results, study tips, coaching, etc. One student reported that he checked his summaries with his mentor. The mentor has a direct impact on the wellbeing of the student: *“She encouraged me when my result wasn’t good. She reassured me that there was still time, and gave tips.”* Although students appreciate the individual meetings with their mentor, the mentor should also be a teaching assistant for their mentee group: *“In the first semester, we saw our mentor once or twice a week, so that we could ask*

questions in the classroom before the lecture would start. (...) This semester, we see her less often, which means we have less contact with her."

In contrast, the relation with the peers is more ambiguous. Most students appreciate that they have access to a higher-year student to ask questions and claim that they would contact them if needed. However, for most students, the contact with their peers is limited to rare messages on social media (mostly from the part of the peer tutors). Yet, the peers are viewed as a role model: *"Every professor mentions in class that we have to start studying early, because it's a lot, it's difficult. But they say that everywhere. (...) So the effect is bigger when you hear it from a higher-year student, because they know it will backfire if you don't."*

Some students claim to have started studying early, but to have left their books as soon as they noticed that they could not keep up with everything. They decided to wait for the exam period, when they had more time to study. Most students refer to bad grades as the most reliable strategy to make them start studying in time. Without tests, it is hard to start. Several students asked for more tests during the semester, although others disagreed, saying they liked the tests as they are organised now because more tests would give them more stress.

One topic came out ad-lib in the focus group discussions. Students in both focus groups spontaneously mentioned the exam review moment, a week after the exams, when students can obtain feedback about their exam from the lecturer. This moment is viewed as valuable, but could be made more efficient. Following improvements were suggested: (1) communicate partial and mean exam results upfront, so that students who need only these results don't have to come to the review moment (leaving more time for other students); (2) hand out exams to 4-5 students at once; (3) organise an online exam review moment.

4 SUMMARY

Although first-year students have a lot to deal with in their first semester of university, the students in our study claim to feel well supported by the campus. Support needs of this group are bigger at the start and end of the first semester, due to the newness of university (October) and the first upcoming exams (December). Tests and trial exams are welcomed, as the students see bad results as the best trigger to start studying. They prefer Q&A sessions in group, to learn from the questions of other students. As for study career guidance, students appreciate the interaction with their mentors who serve as a go-to person for all study-related questions. Due to the newness of their studies and the information overload experienced, first-year students ask to be given information on specific support activities more than once. Activity names should be clear and unambiguous.

The transferability of these results to other campuses or study programs needs to be further researched. We believe it is worthwhile to do so, although a few specific findings might be related to specific campus demographics (e.g. the specific need for good planning of the Q&A sessions seems to be related to the high number of commuting students at KU Leuven Campus De Nayer).

APPENDIX*Table 5. Questions asked in the small-scale quantitative research*

No.	Type	Question
1	Clickable image	Think back to the beginning of the first semester (October). How supported did you feel by our campus as you began your studies?
2	Multiple choice	Below is a list of different forms of course-specific support activities that the campus organises in the first semester. Indicate which ones you have already heard of.
3	Multiple choice	Below is a list of different forms of course-specific support activities that the campus organises in the first semester. Indicate which ones you have participated in.
4	Ranking	Rank the different forms of course-specific support activities for mathematics in the first semester. Put what you consider least valuable at the bottom, and most valuable at the top.
5	Open ended	According to you, what do we have to know if we want to improve the course-specific support activities of the first semester?
6	Multiple choice	Below is a list of other types of support that the campus organises in the first semester. Indicate which ones you have already heard of. (*)
7	Multiple choice	Below is a list of other forms of support that the campus organises in the first semester. Indicate which ones you have participated in. (*)
8	Ranking	Rank the different forms of non-course specific support. Put what you consider least valuable at the bottom, and most valuable at the top. (*)
9	Open ended	According to you, what do we have to know if we want to improve the course-specific support activities of the first semester?

(*) *The tutoring by higher-year students was left out of the questionnaire list at this point. The reasons for this decision were (a) not to overload the list and (b) not to confuse students, as this form of tutoring is strictly speaking not offered by the campus staff but by students.*

REFERENCES

- [1] Malm, J., Bryngfors, L., Mörner, L., (2015), The potential of Supplemental Instruction in engineering education – helping new students to adjust to and succeed in University studies, *European Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 40, No. 4, pp. 347-365.
- [2] Roberts, P., Dunworth, K., (2012), Staff and student perceptions of support services for international students in higher education: a case study, *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, Vol. 34, No. 5, pp. 517-528.
- [3] Harackiewicz, J.M., Priniski, S.J., (2018), Improving Student Outcomes in Higher Education: The Science of Targeted Intervention, *Annu. Rev. Psychol.*, Vol. 69, No. 1, pp. 409-35
- [4] Park, T., Woods, C.S., Hu, S., Bertrand Jones, T., Tandberg, D., (2018), What Happens to Underprepared First-Time-in-College Students When Developmental Education is Optional? The Case of Developmental Math and Intermediate Algebra in the First Semester, *The Journal of Higher Education*,

- Vol. 89, No. 3, pp. 318-340.
- [5] Pinxten, M., Van Soom, C., Peeters, C., De Laet, T., Langie, G., (2017), At-risk at the gate: prediction of study success of first-year science and engineering students in an open-admission university in Flanders – any incremental validity of study strategies?, *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, Vol. 34, No. 1, pp. 45-66.
 - [6] Lee, W.C., Hall, J.L., Godwin, A., Knight, D.B., Verdín, D., (2022), Operationalizing and monitoring student support in undergraduate engineering education, *Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 111, No. 1, pp. 82-110.
 - [7] Knight, G., Powell, N., Woods, G., (2022), Combining diagnostic testing and student mentorship to increase engagement and progression of first-year computer science students, *European Journal of Engineering Education*, DOI: 10.1080/03043797.2022.2063109